

Thermal and non-thermal effects of microwaves in synthesis

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Microwave-assisted reaction is a method generally applicable to syntheses in organic, medicinal and combinatorial chemistry, and compared to conventional method offers enhanced speed, reproducibility and scalability. Microwave-assisted chemistry is a key technique that has made a significant contribution to the thermal and non-thermal control of synthetic reactions for the past many years by speeding up reaction times from days to merely minutes. An overview of the thermal effects and non-thermal microwave effects is presented in this article.

Keywords: Thermal, non-thermal, reproducibility, scalability, microwave, synthesis.

1. Introduction

Microwave-assisted organic synthesis has come into sight as a new "lead" in organic chemistry. The technique offers simple, clean, fast, efficient and economic for the synthesis of a large number of organic molecules. In the recent years, microwave-assisted organic reaction has emerged as new tool in synthesis of new or known products. Important advantage of this technology include highly accelerated rate of the reaction, reduction in reaction time with an improvement in the yield and quality of the product. Now day's this technique is considered as an important approach towards green chemistry, because this technique is more environmentally friendly. This technology is widely used in the laboratory and has a large impact on the fields of screening, combinatorial chemistry, medicinal chemistry and drug development. Conventional method of organic synthesis usually needs longer heating time, tedious apparatus setup, which results in higher cost of process and the excessive use of solvents or reagents lead to environmental pollution. This growth of green chemistry holds significant potential for a reduction of the by product, a reduction in waste production and a lowering of the energy costs.

Due to its ability to couple directly with the reactant molecules and by passing thermal conductivity leading to a rapid rise in the temperature, microwave irradiation has been used to improve many organic syntheses¹. Microwave heating is very attractive for chemical applications and has become a widely accepted non-conventional energy source for performing organic synthesis. This statement is supported by the increasing availability of new and reliable microwave instrumentation. A large number of examples of reactions have been described in organic synthesis. Several reviews have been published on the application of microwaves to solvent-free reactions^{2,3}, cycloaddition reactions⁴, the synthesis of radioisotopes⁵, fullerene chemistry^{6,7}, polymers⁸, heterocyclic chemistry⁹⁻¹², homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis^{13,14}, medicinal and combinatorial chemistry¹⁵⁻²⁰ and green chemistry²¹⁻²⁴.

1.1. Microwaves:

Microwaves are electromagnetic waves that have a frequency range from around 0.3 GHz (there is no actual specified lower frequency limit) to 300 GHz with corresponding wavelengths ranging from 1 m to 1 mm. Microwaves are coherent and polarised in contrast to visible waves (apart from

lasers). They obey the laws of optics and can be transmitted, absorbed or reflected depending on the type of material²⁵ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The interaction of microwaves with different materials.

Traditionally, organic reactions are heated using an external heat source (such as an oil bath), and therefore, heat is transferred by conduction. This is a comparatively slow and inefficient method for transferring energy into the system because it depends on the thermal conductivity of the various materials that must be penetrated, and results in the temperature of the reaction vessel being higher than that of the reaction mixture. In contrast, microwave irradiation produces efficient internal heating by direct coupling of microwave energy with the polar molecules (for example, solvents, reagents and catalysts) that are present in the reaction mixture²⁶ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Mechanism of heating process in conventional and microwave process.

1.2. Microwave heating:

Even now, the clear-cut molecular explanation of microwave heating is ill-defined, but the accepted general descrip-

tion of how microwave energy is converted into heat energy is sufficient for most purposes. Chemists are often told that microwave ovens are tuned to a frequency where water molecules absorb microwaves into rotational energy levels, leading to heating. This is a common misunderstanding and it is important to realise that it is gaseous water that has quantized rotational energy levels in the microwave region. In the liquid state, for all practical purposes, the quantization of rotational levels is non-existent. If we temporarily neglect the quantization of microwaves, the easiest way to visualise microwave heating is to picture a microwave for what it is: a high-frequency oscillating electric and magnetic field. Any material that may be electrically or magnetically polarised at this oscillation frequency will be affected to some extent by these microwave fields. The precise nature of the heating will depend on whether the material comprises discrete molecules, assemblies of polar molecules or an extended lattice.

Microwave heating alleged effects can be divided into two types, namely thermal and non-thermal effects. Thermal effects are those caused by the different temperature regions within a sample, which are as a result of microwave dielectric heating. Non-thermal effects are those caused by effects specifically inherent to the microwaves and are not caused by different temperature regimes. These effects (non-thermal) are normally associated with microwave spectroscopy. However, microwave dielectric heating differs from microwave spectroscopy, which is carried out in the gas phase and for which discrete energy levels of excitation can be observed. This is in contrast to dielectric heating during which no molecules can be excited into higher energy levels. Therefore microwave dielectric heating should not be confused with microwave spectroscopy²⁷.

Microwave heating can be divided into two types such as thermal effects and non-thermal effects. Thermal effect is caused by different temperature regime which can be created due to microwave dielectric heating whereas non-thermal effects is caused by effects specifically inherent to the microwaves and are not caused by different temperature regime. Non-thermal effects are several times more harmful than thermal effects. But, many believe non-thermal effects are good for synthesis. The current exposure safety standards are mainly based on the thermal effects, which are inadequate.

1.3. Thermal effects:

Thermal effects happen from the different characteristics of microwave dielectric heating and conventional heating. Microwave heating uses the ability of some compounds (liquids or solids) to transform electromagnetic energy into heat. Energy transmission is created by dielectric losses, which is in contrast to conduction and convection processes observed in conventional heating. The magnitude of heating depends on the dielectric properties of the molecules, also in contrast to conventional heating. These characteristics mean that absorption of the radiation and heating may be performed selectively. Microwave irradiation is rapid and volumetric, with the whole material heated simultaneously. In contrast, conventional heating is slow and is introduced into the sample from the surface. The thermal effects observed under microwave irradiation conditions are a result of the inverted heat transfer, the homogeneities of the microwave field within the sample and the selective absorption of the radiation by polar compounds. These effects can be used efficiently to improve processes, modify selectivity or even to perform reactions that do not occur under classical conditions²⁸.

Dielectric heating ensues from the tendency of dipoles (mostly water molecules in addition to reactants) to follow the inversion of alternating electric fields and induce energy dissipation in the form of heat through molecular friction and dielectric loss, which allows more regular repartition in reaction temperatures compared to conventional heating (Fig. 3). Antonio and Deam recently proposed a new hypothesis based on enhanced diffusion that stated "If the transport of an active species is a rate limiting step in a reaction (such as for diffusion limited reactions), and if microwave enhances the diffusion of that species, then overall reaction rate would change under microwave heating compared with conventional heating". Particularly, various organic reactions can be carried out in an aqueous medium using MW irradiation without using any phase-transfer catalyst (PTC). This is because water at higher temperature behaves as a pseudo-organic solvent, as the dielectric constant decreases substantially and an ionic product increases the solvating power towards organic molecules to be similar to that of ethanol or acetone²⁹.

More efficient energetic coupling of solvent with microwaves promotes followings.

Fig. 3. Effect of microwaves on the reaction mixture in aqueous medium.

- Higher rate of temperature
- Inverted heat transfer and volumetric
- Hot spots in monomode microwaves
- Selective on properties of material such as solvents, catalysts, reagents, intermediates, products, susceptors etc.

Loss Tangent (Energy Dissipation Factor) is a measure of the ability to absorb microwave energy and convert it into thermal energy (heat). It is derived from Maxwell's equation. The reaction medium with high $\tan \delta$ value provides efficient absorption of microwave radiation by reagents and catalysts with rapid heating. Superheating effects of solvents at atmospheric pressure with elimination of wall effects.

$$\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$$

where d = dissipation factor, ϵ''

= loss factor and ϵ'

= dielectric constant.

1.4. Overheating:

Overheating of polar liquids is an effect that can be exploited practically. Mingos detected this effect in polar liquids on using microwaves, where overheating in the range 13–26°C above the normal boiling point may occur. This effect can be explained by the "inverted heat transfer" effect since boiling nuclei are formed at the surface of the liquid. This effect could explain the enhancement in reaction rates observed in organic and organometallic chemistry. This thermal effect, which is not easily reproduced by conventional

heating (or impossible to reproduce), can be used to improve the yields and the efficiency of certain processes³⁰.

1.5. "Hot spots" inhomogeneities:

Various authors have detected the presence of "hot spots" in samples irradiated with microwaves. Similarly, hot spots are also postulated. This is a thermal effect that arises as a consequence of the inhomogeneity of the applied field, resulting in the temperature in certain zones within the sample being much greater than the macroscopic temperature. These regions are not representative of the reaction conditions as a whole. This overheating effect has been demonstrated by Mingos in the decomposition of H₂S over γ -Al₂O₃ and MoS₂- γ -Al₂O₃. The conversion efficiency under microwave and conventional thermal conditions are compared. The higher conversion under microwave irradiation was attributed to the presence of hot spots. They estimated the temperature in the hot spots to be about 100–200°C higher than the bulk temperature. This temperature difference was determined by calculations and on the basis of several transformations observed, such as the transition of γ - to α -alumina and the melting of MoS₂, which happen at temperatures greatly higher than the measured bulk temperature. The size of the hot spots was calculated approximately to be as large as 100 mm. Hot spots may be created by the difference in dielectric properties of materials, by the uneven distribution of electromagnetic field strength, or by volumetric dielectric heating under microwave conditions^{31–34}.

Hihn *et al.* studied the temperature distribution in the preparation of coumaran-2-one in solvent-free conditions. They divided the volume into three layers of equal thickness. The use of this segmentation allowed them to apply a kinetic law in each cell, where the temperature is considered to be homogeneous. Higher temperature heterogeneity was found at the end of the reaction during microwave heating than on heating with an oil bath. These temperature inhomogeneities during microwave heating are mainly due to the use of a monomode cavity. Their results demonstrated that the difference between microwaves and standard oil bath heating only concerns the temperature repartition. From the point of view of global energy balance, the fact is that microwave heating leads to higher performance because the power consumed is directly useful to the reaction mixture but less so to intermediates such as a caloric fluid³⁵.

1.6. Selective heating:

1.6.1. Solvents:

Microwave irradiation is a selective mode of heating. Normally, microwaves generate rapid intense heating of polar substances while non polar substances do not absorb the radiation and are not heated. Selective heating has been exploited in solvents, catalysts and reagents. Strauss³⁶ carries out a Hoffmann elimination using a two-phase water/chloroform system. The reaction performed in water at 105°C led to polymerisation of the final product. However, the reaction proceeds nicely under microwave irradiation in a two phase water/chloroform system. The temperatures of the aqueous and organic phases were 110 and 50°C, respectively, due to differences in the dielectric properties of the solvents. This difference avoids the decomposition of the final product. Comparable conditions are difficult to obtain by traditional heating methods. A similar effect was observed by Hallberg in the preparation of β,β -diarylated aldehydes by hydrolysis of enol ethers in a two phase (toluene/aqueous HCl) system³⁷.

Marken *et al.* showed that the effect of 2.45 GHz microwave radiation on electroorganic processes in microwave absorbing (organic) media can be dramatic but is predominantly thermal in nature³⁸. They studied the oxidation of 2 mM ferrocene in acetonitrile (0.1 M NBu₄PF₆) with a Pt electrode. Sigmoidal steady-state responses were detected and, as expected, increasing the microwave power led to an increase in the limiting current. This effect has been qualitatively attributed to the formation of a "hot spot" in close proximity to the electrode surface. Focusing of microwaves at the end of the metal electrode is responsible for this highly localized thermal effect. Switching off the microwave power results in a return to the voltammetric characteristics observed at room temperature. The temperature can be seen to increase away from the electrode surface with a "hot spot" region at a distance of approximately 40 mm. The "hot spot" temperature was 118°C and is considerably higher than the boiling point of acetonitrile (81.6°C) and also much higher than the temperature of the electrode (47°C). Under these conditions the velocity of acetonitrile convection through the "hot spot" region is 0.1 cm s⁻¹ and therefore, the solvent typically passes through the high-temperature region in less than 100 ms. Hot spots have been also postulated in terms of temperature gradients within a solid^{39,40}.

1.6.2. Stability of catalyst:

Since MW-assisted reactions are rapid, the residence time of nano-catalyst at high temperature is minimal. Catalytic processes with shorter reaction times safeguard the catalyst from deactivation and decomposition, consequently increasing the overall competence of the catalyst, as well as the entire protocol. Selective heating has been exploited efficiently in heterogeneous reactions to heat selectively a polar catalyst. For example, Bogdal describes the oxidation of alcohols using Magtrieve. The irradiation of Magtrieve led to rapid heating of the material up to 360°C within 2 min. When toluene was introduced into the reaction vessel, the temperature of Magtrieve reached at 140°C within 2 min and was more uniformly distributed. This experiment showed that the temperature of the catalyst can be higher than the bulk temperature of the solvent, which implies that such a process might be more energy efficient than other conventional processes^{41,42}.

This overheating effect was also determined by Auerbach⁴³ through equilibrium molecular dynamics and non-equilibrium molecular dynamics in zeolite-guest systems after experimental work by Conner. At equilibrium all atoms in the system are at the same temperature. In contrast, when Na-Y zeolite is exposed to MW energy, the effective steady-state temperature of Na atoms is considerably higher than that of the rest of the framework, indicating a non-thermal energy distribution. The steady-state temperature for binary methanol-benzene mixtures in both siliceous zeolites is studied. Their result suggested that methanol dissipates energy to benzene, though much too slowly to approach thermal equilibrium while under steady-state conditions. However, some controversy also exists concerning the effects of microwave irradiation in heterogeneous catalysis. Some authors have proposed the modification of the catalyst's electronic properties upon exposure to microwave irradiation in order to explain the superior catalytic properties of catalysts under these conditions. However, other authors have reported that microwave irradiation has no effect on the reaction kinetics⁴⁴.

1.6.3. Reagents and products:

Larhed⁴⁵ described the molybdenum-catalysed allylic alkylation of (*E*)-3-phenyl-2-propenyl acetate. The reaction occurs with good reproducibility, complete conversion and

high yields only a few minutes. In the standard solvent (THF) and with an irradiation power of 250 W, a yield of 87% was obtained and high regioselectivity and enantiomeric excess (98%) were achieved. Somewhat lower regioselectivities (17–19: 1) than in the previously reported two-step method (32–49: 1) were obtained. Alkylation also worked on polymer-supported reagents and, consequently, can be applied in combinatorial chemistry. The high temperature obtained (220°C) is not only due to increased boiling points at elevated pressure, but also to a significant contribution from sustained overheating. The yields from the oil bath experiments are lower than those for the corresponding microwave-heated reactions. In the case of pure, microwave-transparent solvents, the added substances, may be ionic or non-ionic, must therefore, contribute to the overall temperature profile when the reaction is carried out. It seems reasonable that when the substrates act as “molecular radiators” in channeling energy from microwave radiation to bulk heat, their reactivity might be enhanced. The concept and advantages of “molecular radiators” have also been described by other authors⁴⁶.

1.6.4. Catalyst as susceptors:

A susceptor can be used when the reagents and solvents do not absorb microwave radiation. A susceptor is an inert compound that efficiently absorbs microwave radiation and transfers the thermal energy to another compound that is a poor absorber of the radiation. This method is associated with an interesting advantage. If the susceptor is a catalyst, the energy can be focused on the surface of the susceptor where the reaction takes place. In this way, thermal decomposition of sensitive compounds can be avoided. In contrast, transmission of the energy occurs through conventional mechanisms. In solvent-free or heterogeneous conditions graphite has been used as a susceptor. For example, Garrigues⁴⁷ described the cyclization of (+)-citronellal to (2)-isopulegol and (+)-neoisopulegol on graphite.

The stereoselectivity of the cyclization can be altered under microwave irradiation. (2)-Isopulegol is always the principal diastereoisomer regardless of the method of heating, but the use of microwaves increases the amount of (+)-neoisopulegol up to 30%. Kappe⁴⁸ and Leadbeater⁴⁹ have used silicon carbide and ionic liquid, respectively, as susceptors and determined that addition of these materials to the reaction mixture enhanced its overall capacity to ab-

sorb MWs and significantly reduced the required MW energy. The addition of these materials as susceptors to the reaction mixture, however, adds to the overall cost of the protocol and makes it expensive. Ideally, if nanomaterials can play a dual role of catalyst and susceptor then all the interesting advantages related to it can be enjoyed without the need for additional material as a susceptor. This can be achieved by using a nano-catalyst, such as a polar ferrite-based material, which can act not only as a catalyst but also as a susceptor.

Ionic liquids have been used both in solution and under homogeneous conditions. For example, Ley⁵⁰ described the preparation of thioamides from amides. Although the reaction under classical conditions occurs in excellent yield, the reaction time can be shortened using microwave irradiation. The reaction was performed in toluene and, as this is not an optimum solvent for the absorption and dissipation of microwave energy, a small amount of an ionic liquid solvent was added to the reaction mixture to ensure efficient heat distribution.

In this regard, Leadbeater⁵¹ studied the use of ionic liquids as aids for the microwave heating of a nonpolar solvent. It was shown that apolar solvents can, in a very short time, be heated to temperatures way above their boiling points in sealed vessels using a small quantity of an ionic liquid. It was found that 0.2 mmol of ionic liquid was the optimal amount to heat 2 mL of solvent. These solvent mixtures were tested with some model reactions such as Diels-Alder cycloadditions, Michael additions and alkylation reactions.

1.7. Non-thermal effects:

Non-thermal effects have been envisaged to have several origins, including thermodynamic parameters. Molecular shake-up and movement are other. Fundamentals of aqueous Microwave Chemistry factors that have contribute to the MW effect. Such effects can also occur from the interactions of microwaves and reactants, like thermal effects. It is very difficult to isolate non-thermal effects from thermal effects.

Loupy⁵² has published a tentative rationalization of non-thermal effects. The nature of the microwave effect was studied and classified considering the reaction medium (polar and apolar solvents and solvent-free reactions) and the reaction mechanism, i.e. the polarity of the transition state (isopolar and polar transition states) and the transition state

position along the reaction coordinate. Microwave effects should increase in apolar solvents and solvent-free reactions, with polar transition states and late transition states. Perreux and Loupy⁵³ have researched non-thermal effects on the basis of the reaction medium (polar and non-polar) and the polarity of the transition state. They have established that the MW effect increases in non-polar solvents and solvent-free reactions and reactions with polar transition states. This effect has also been demonstrated by Polshettiwar and Kaushik⁵⁴ using a "tighter ion pair effect" in aminolysis of enolizable esters. They observed that reactions involving tighter ion pairs (e.g. $C_6H_{11}NH-K^+$) had higher reaction rates, indicating more MW-specific effect, than reactions involving less tight ion pairs (e.g. $C_6H_5NH-K^+$). This may be due to delocalization of negative charge on the aromatic ring of aniline (as compared to aliphatic cyclohexyl amine), making the transition state less polar.

However, non-thermal effects may arise also from interactions between the microwave field and the material, similar to thermal effects. In this regard, microwave heating strongly interferes with possible non-thermal effects and these cannot be easily separated in mechanistic studies. Various authors have proposed that changes in thermodynamic parameters under microwave irradiation are the cause of the "microwave effect". Nevertheless, doubt has subsequently been cast on some of these theories by other authors and indeed, by the original authors as well. Jacob *et al.*⁵⁵ published a review on synthetic results to which the microwave effect has been attributed.

Fig. 4. Non-thermal effects in microwave synthesis.

Berlan *et al.*⁵⁶ found that in cycloaddition reactions carried out under reflux in xylene or dibutyl ether at the same temperature, the reaction rates were always faster under microwave conditions than when using classical heating methods. The observed acceleration is more significant in apolar solvents, which show weak dielectric losses. Subsequently, Strauss *et al.* indicated that the kinetics of these and other reactions are similar under microwave irradiation and classical heating, which would mean that there is no specific microwave effect.

Hajek *et al.*⁵⁷ studied the halogenation of alkenes with tetrahalomethanes in homogeneous conditions and found that the highest rate enhancements were recorded in the presence of polar solvents. In these homogeneous conditions, rate enhancement seems to be caused mainly by a thermal dielectric heating effect resulting from the effective coupling of microwaves to polar solvents. In heterogeneous reactions the presence of hot spots and selective heating should be responsible for the observed acceleration. This effect was also observed in the alkylation of secondary amines on zeolites, where temperature gradients of up to 20°C were observed in the samples.

Kappe *et al.*⁵⁸ performed a reinvestigation of microwave assisted RCM. They showed that absorption of microwave radiation by the Grubbs catalyst was negligible and, in contrast, the diene showed significant microwave absorption and acted as a molecular radiator. However, it was also demonstrated that under thermal conditions the results corresponded to those obtained in the microwave heating experiments. This showed that it is unimportant whether the energy is directly transferred to one of the reactants or to the bulk solvent by thermal microwave heating.

Furthermore, Kappe's results from a study of the Biginelli reaction are clear; the kinetic experiments show that there is no appreciable difference in reaction rates and yields between reactions carried out under microwave irradiation and thermal heating at identical temperatures. This result is understandable since a polar solvent (ethanol) was used, meaning that the radiation was absorbed by the solvent and thermal energy transmitted to the reagents by conventional mechanisms (convection and conduction) rather than by dielectric losses.

Miklavc *et al.*⁵⁹ has observed a decrease in activation energy during MW-assisted decomposition of sodium bicar-

bonate. The exposure of substrates (dielectric materials) to microwaves induced rapid rotation of the molecules. This in turn generated heat due to friction and also increased the probability of contact between reactant molecules, thus enhancing the reaction rate by reducing the activation energy. In continuation of this work, Cross *et al.*⁶⁰ found an increase in molecular mobility in the presence of microwaves. The increase in the rate of reactions was due to an increase in the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor.

In this respect, both Berlan and Strauss⁶¹ rule out the possibility that microwave radiation can excite rotational transitions. When a compound absorbs microwaves, the dielectric heating causes an increase in the temperature of the system. When the internal energy of the system is raised it is distributed among translational, rotational or vibrational energies regardless of the mode of heating. Consequently, it was concluded that kinetic differences should not be expected between reactions heated by microwaves or by classical heating if the temperature is known and the solution is thermally homogeneous.

Similarly, Stuerger *et al.*⁶² indicated that absorption of microwave photons cannot induce any chemical bond breaking and the electric field is too low to lead to induced organization. Moreover, in condensed phases the collision rate induces transfer between rotational and vibrational phases. Hence, it was concluded that an electric field cannot produce any molecular effect. Molecular effects resulting from the microwave field could, however, be observed for a medium that does not heat under microwave irradiation.

However, after studying the synthesis of titanium carbide, Cross⁶³ concluded that molecular mobility can increase in the presence of a microwave field and that in this case it is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor A that changes and not the energy of activation.

The use of microwaves leads to a temperature reduction of 80–100°C in the sintering temperature of partially stabilized zirconia, an effect that is non-thermal in nature. Wroe *et al.*⁶⁴ showed that a microwave field improves either the volume or grain-boundary mechanism rather than improving diffusion at the surface, that is dominant at low temperatures. Microwaves preferentially increase the flux of vacancies within grain boundaries in the sample.

Other examples have been found of results that cannot be explained solely by a thermal effect. In a study on the

mutarotation of α -D-glucose to β -D-glucose, Pagnota⁶⁵ found that in EtOH-H₂O (1:1) the use of microwaves led, apart from a more rapid equilibration compared to conventional heating, to a modification of the equilibrium position to a point where a larger amount of α -D-glucose was obtained than under classical heating. This extraordinary effect cannot be explained by a classical heating effect and is the clearest example of a possible specific action created by a microwave radiation field.

Another interesting study was reported by Zhang on the synthesis of aromatic esters by esterification of benzoic acids in refluxing alcohols. The authors used microwave radiation at a frequency of 1 GHz, where there is no microwave heating action but only an a thermal microwave effect. Interestingly, under these conditions a reduction in reaction time was still observed. Other reports include non-thermal effects in solid phase separation processes, partitioning of *p*-nitroaniline between pseudo-phases, structural transformations in amphiphilic bilayers, and protein-catalysed esterifications and *trans*-esterifications.

Conclusion

The progress of microwaves technology in organic synthesis is due to environment-friendly process. The various organic reactions achieved under microwave irradiation are gaining popularity, because it provides clean, fast, efficient and economic for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds. This technique facilitates a number of reactions to occur in shorter reaction times with higher yields and clean products. In the near future, microwave-assisted organic reactions can be performed on industrial scales so as to enhance the efficiency of the chemical reactions. The debate of whether microwave-induced process is thermal or non-thermal would certainly continue. It is also understandable that some authors would find evidences in favor of thermal effects and some would not. The most important part is to realize that reactions are highly specific and therefore, effects on reactions by a source of energy should be very specific too. It may not be possible to define microwave effects as thermal and non-thermal using the literature so far appeared. Therefore, clear explanation of these effects in chemical reactions need to be identified in the future. In the meantime, it is established that microwave irradiation and heating method has emerged as one of the most important tools in chemical research.

References

1. R. S. Varma, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2001, **73**, 193.
2. A. Loupy, G. Bram and J. Sansoulet, *New J. Chem.*, 1992, **16**, 233.
3. R. S. Varma, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 1235.
4. A. Diaz-Ortiz, F. Langa, A. de la Hoz and A. Moreno, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **4**, 3659.
5. N. Elander, J. R. Jones, S. Y. Lu and S. Stone-Elander, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2000, **29**, 239.
6. F. Langa, P. de la Cruz, E. Espildora, J. J. Garcia, M. C. Perez and A. de la Hoz, *Carbon*, 2000, **38**, 1641.
7. F. Langa, P. de la Cruz, E. Espildora and A. de la Hoz, "Applications of Microwave Irradiation to Fullerene Chemistry, in Fullerenes", The Electrochemical Society, New York, 2000, **9**, 168.
8. L. Zong, S. Zhou, N. Sgriccia, M. C. Hawley and L. C. Kempel, *J. Microwave Power Electromagn. Energy*, 2003, **38**, 49.
9. Y. Xu and Q.-X. Guo, *Heterocycles*, 2004, **63**, 903.
10. N. N. Romanova, P. V. Kudan, A. G. Gravis and Y. G. Bundel, *Chem. Heterocycl. Compd.*, 2000, **36**, 1130.
11. A. R. Katritzky and S. K. Singh, *ARKIVOC*, 2003, **xiii**, 68.
12. A. Corsaro, U. Chiacchio, V. Pistara and G. Romeo, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **8**, 511.
13. M. Larhed, C. Moberg and A. Hallberg, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2002, **35**, 717.
14. H. Will, P. Scholz and B. Ondruschka, *Chem.-Ing.-Tech.*, 2002, **74**, 1057.
15. C. O. Kappe, *Comb. Chem.*, 2002, **6**, 314.
16. M. Lahred and A. Hallberg, *Drug Discovery Today*, 2001, **6**, 406.
17. A. Lew, P. O. Krutzik, M. E. Hart and A. R. Chamberlin, *J. Comb. Chem.*, 2002, **4**, 95.
18. C. O. Kappe, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.*, 2002, **6**, 314.
19. B. Wathey, J. Tierney, P. Lidstrom and J. Westman, *Drug Discovery Today*, 2002, **7**, 373.
20. H. E. Blackwell, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2003, **1**, 1251.
21. R. S. Varma, *Clean Products and Processes*, 1999, 132.
22. R. S. Varma, in "Advances in Green Chemistry: Chemical Syntheses Using Microwave Irradiation", Astra Zeneca Research Foundation, Kavitha Printers, Bangalore, India, 2002.
23. A. K. Bose, M. S. Manhas, S. N. Ganguly, A. H. Sharma and B. K. Banik, *Synthesis*, 2002, 1578.
24. M. Nuchter, B. Ondruschka, W. Bonrath and A. Gum, *Green Chem.*, 2004, **6**, 128.
25. Biswajit Chandra Das, Debjit Bhowmik and Subhasish Chaudhuri, *Pharma Innovation*, 2012, **1(6)**, 1.
26. C. O. Kappe, D. Dallinger and S. S. Murphree, "Practical microwave synthesis for organic chemists", Wiley-VCH,

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- Weinheim, 2009, pp. 11-42.
27. C. Gabriel, S. Gabriel, E. H. Grant, B. S. J. Halstead and D. M. P. Mingos, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1998, **27**, 213.
 28. C. Antonio and R. T. Deam, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2007, **9**, 2976.
 29. C. R. Strauss and R. W. Trainor, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1995, **48**, 1665.
 30. E. Abtal, M. Lallemand, G. Bertrand and G. Watelle, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 381.
 31. D. R. Baghurst and D. M. P. Mingos, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 674.
 32. X. Zhang, D. O. Hayward and D. M. P. Mingos, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, 975.
 33. X. Zhang, D. O. Hayward and D. M. P. Mingos, *Catal. Lett.*, 2003, **88**, 33.
 34. P. Goncalo, J.-Y. Hihn, R. Vienet, P. Nika and J. Vebrel, *J. Nature*, 2001, **13**, 19.
 35. K. D. Raner, C. R. Strauss and R. W. Trainor, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 2456.
 36. P. Nilsson, M. Larhed and A. Hallberg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 8217.
 37. Y. C. Tsai, B. A. Coles, R. G. Compton and F. Marken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 9784.
 38. D. Bogdal, M. Lukasiewicz, J. Pielichowski, A. Miciak and Sz. Bednarz, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 649.
 39. M. Lukasiewicz, D. Bogdal and J. Pielichowska, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2003, **345**, 1269.
 40. N. F. K. Kaiser, U. Bremberg, M. Larhed, C. Moberg and A. Hallberg, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 3595.
 41. D. Bogdal, M. Lukasiewicz, J. Pielichowski, A. Miciak and Sz. Bednarz, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 649.
 42. C. Blanco and S. M. Auerbach, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 6250.
 43. M. D. Turner, R. L. Laurence, W. C. Conner and K. S. Yngvesson, *AIChE J.*, 2000, **46**, 758.
 44. N. F. K. Kaiser, U. Bremberg, M. Larhed, C. Moberg and A. Hallberg, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 3595.
 45. A. Steinber, A. Stadlet, S. F. Mayer, K. Faber and C. O. Kappe, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 6283.
 46. B. Garrigues, R. Laurent, C. Laporte, A. Laporterie and J. Dubac, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1996, 743.
 47. T. Razzaq, J. M. Kremsner and C. O. Kappe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 6321.
 48. N. E. Leadbeater and H. M. Torrenius, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 3145.
 49. S. V. Ley, A. G. Leach and R. I. Storer, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 2001, **1**, 358.
 50. N. E. Leadbeater and H. M. Torrenius, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 3145.
 51. A. Loupy and R. S. Varma, *Chim. Oggi*, 2006, **24**, 36.
 52. L. Perreux and A. Loupy, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 9199.
 53. V. Polshettiwar and M. P. Kaushik, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2005, **44B**, 773.
 54. J. Jacob, L. H. L. Chia and F. Y. C. Boey, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1995, **30**, 5321.
 55. J. Berlan, P. Giboreau, S. Lefevre and C. Marchand, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 2363.
 56. M. Hajek, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1997, **62**, 347.
 57. S. Garbacia, B. Desai, O. Lavaster and C. O. Kappe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 9136.
 58. A. Miklavc, *Chem. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 552.
 59. J. G. P. Binner, N. A. Hassine and T. E. Cross, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1995, **30**, 5389.
 60. K. D. Raner, C. R. Strauss, F. Vyskoc and L. Mokbel, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 950.
 61. D. A. C. Stuerger and P. Gaillard, *J. Microwave Power Electromagn. Energy*, 1996, **31**, 101.
 62. J. G. P. Binner, N. A. Hassine and T. E. Cross, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1995, **30**, 5389.
 63. R. Wroe and A. T. Rowley, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1996, **31**, 2019.
 64. M. Pagnota, C. L. F. Pooley, B. Gurland and M. Choi, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **6**, 407.
 65. Z. B. Zhang, L. X. Zhou, M. Zhang, H. Wu and Z. J. Chen, *Synth. Commun.*, 2001, **31**, 2435.

